

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation & communication, & progress report/D7.2

WP 7, T 7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4, 7.5

Authors: Lorenzo Morelli (ICONS); Sofia Francescutto (ICONS); Federica Fusco (ICONS)

Technical references

Project Acronym	INHERIT
Project Title	Next Generation Solutions for Sustainable, Inclusive, Resource-efficient, and Resilient Cultural Heritage
Project Coordinator	Stamatia Rizou SingularLogic S.A srizou@singularlogic.eu
Project Duration	October 2023 – March 2027 (42 months)
Deliverable No.	D7.2
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 7 - Dissemination, exploitation, and communication
Task	T7.1; T7.2; T7.3; T7.4; T7.5
Lead beneficiary	ICONS (8)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	UPRC (4); ICLEI (6); EAHTR (18)
Due date of deliverable	30 June 2025
Actual submission date	27 June 2025

* PU = Public

SEN = Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author	Contribution
1.0	1/04/2025	ICONS	Federica Fusco, Lorenzo Morelli	First draft
2.0	30/05/2025	ICONS	Sofia Francescutto, Lorenzo Morelli	Revised and updated version
3.0	01/06/2025	ICONS	Ani Asatryan, Erica Moresco	Internal review
4.0	09/06/2025	UPRC, ICLEI	Dimitra Aglamisi (UPRC), Telmo Jiménez Irizar, Gioele Racca (ICLEI)	Task leads contribution
5.0	23/06/2025	SLG	Antonia Vronti	Peer review
6.0	24/06/2025	ICLEI	Telmo Jiménez Irizar	Peer review
7.0	24/06/2025	ICONS	Sofia Francescutto	Final document

Table of contents

Table of contents	3
Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction.....	10
1.1. Update on Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) activities.....	10
1.2. Methodology.....	12
1.2.1. Identification of KERs and IPR management	13
1.2.2. Stakeholder mapping	14
1.2.3. Dissemination strategies.....	14
1.2.4. Exploitation strategies	15
2. KERs, exploitation strategies and stakeholder mapping.....	16
2.1. Introduction	16
2.2. Cluster 1: monitoring and inspection tools and platform	17
2.2.1. KERs and exploitation strategies.....	17
2.2.2. Stakeholder mapping	18
2.2.2.1. Provision of service	19
2.2.2.2. TRL upscaling.....	20
2.2.2.3. Knowledge transfer.....	21
2.3. Cluster 2: modernisation services	21
2.3.1. KERs and exploitation strategies.....	21
2.3.2. Stakeholder mapping	24
2.3.2.1. Provision of service	24
2.3.2.2. Replication	25
2.3.2.3. TRL upscaling.....	26
2.4. Cluster 3: SSH and communication materials.....	27
2.4.1. KERs and exploitation strategies.....	27
2.4.2. Stakeholder mapping	28
2.4.2.1. Academic exploitation and knowledge transfer	28
2.4.2.2. Replication	29
2.5. Cluster 4: Pilot implementation	30
2.5.1. KERs and exploitation strategies.....	30
2.5.2. Stakeholder mapping	30
2.5.2.1. Replication	30
3. Dissemination strategy.....	32
3.1. Prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies	32
3.1.1. Cluster 1: dissemination strategies.....	33
3.1.2. Cluster 2: dissemination strategies.....	35
3.1.3. Cluster 3: dissemination strategies.....	37
3.1.4. Cluster 4: dissemination strategies.....	39

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

3.2. Clustering, synergies and events attendance.....	41
3.2.1. Collaboration plan.....	42
4. Communication activities: progress and impact.....	44
4.1. Monitoring methodology and Community Engagement Index (CEI)	44
4.2. Website.....	44
4.2.1. Website Engagement Index (WEI) and monitoring	45
4.3. Social Media.....	47
4.3.1. Social Engagement Index (SEI) and monitoring	47
4.4. Editorial publications.....	49
4.4.1. Publication Engagement Index (PEI) and monitoring	50
4.5. Timeline	52
5. C&D Local Desks	53
5.1. Local C&D strategies and plans	53
5.1.1. C&D Local Desks: definition and purpose	53
5.1.2. Roles and responsibilities of the Secretariat	53
5.1.3. Roles and responsibilities of the Local Desks	54
5.1.4. Local Desks composition, setup and maintenance.....	54
5.1.5. A tailored C&D strategy for Local Desks	55
5.1.5.1. Channels.....	56
5.1.5.2. C&D Formats and materials.....	56
5.1.5.3. Events and Clustering.....	58
6. Conclusions.....	59
Annexes.....	61
Annex 1 – Local C&D strategies	61
6.1.1. Pilot: Jastrebarsko, Croatia	61
6.1.2. Pilot: Athens, Greece	63
6.1.3. Pilot: Riga, Latvia	65
6.1.4. Pilot: Gdynia, Poland.....	67
6.1.5. Pilot: Valladolid, Spain	69
6.1.6. Pilot: Visby, Sweden	71
6.1.7. Pilot: Izmir, Turkey	72

List of Tables

Table 1 Overview of prioritised stakeholders per cluster.....	8
Table 2 Update of the project’s CDE activities.....	11
Table 3 Process of KER and IPR mapping overview	14
Table 4 Exploitation strategy KER2	17
Table 5 Exploitation strategy KER5	18
Table 6 Exploitation strategy KER4	22
Table 7 Exploitation strategy KER5	22
Table 8 Exploitation strategy KER5	23
Table 9 Exploitation strategy KER8	23
Table 10 Exploitation strategy KER1	27
Table 11 Exploitation strategy KER9	27
Table 12 Exploitation strategy KER10	27
Table 13 Exploitation strategy KER11	30
Table 14 Prioritised stakeholders per cluster	32
Table 15 Cluster 1: prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies.....	33
Table 16 Cluster 2: prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies.....	35
Table 17 Cluster 3: prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies.....	37
Table 18 Cluster 4: prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies.....	39
Table 19 Collaboration plan	42
Table 20 Community Engagement Index (CEI)	44
Table 21 Website Engagement Index (WEI)	45
Table 22 Communication strategy - website	46
Table 23 Social Engagement Index (SEI)	48
Table 24 Outreach and engagement by platform	48
Table 25 Posts and followers by platform	48
Table 26 Communication strategy – social media	49
Table 27 Publication engagement index (PEI)	50
Table 28 Outreach and engagement by type	50
Table 29 Communication strategy – editorial publications.....	51
Table 30 Timeline of communication activities	52
Table 31 Local Desks composition	54
Table 32 C&D formats for Local Desks.....	57
Table 33 Overview of INHERIT's CDE next steps.....	59

List of Figures

Figure 1 Integrated approach structure.....	13
Figure 2 INHERIT results clusters	16
Figure 3 Cluster 1 – Provision of service stakeholders	19
Figure 4 Cluster 1 – TRL upscaling stakeholders.....	20
Figure 5 Cluster 1 – Knowledge transfer stakeholder	21
Figure 6 Cluster 2 - Provision of service stakeholders	24
Figure 7 Cluster 2 - Replication stakeholders	25

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Figure 8 Cluster 2 - TRL upsclaing stakeholders.....	26
Figure 9 Cluster 3 - Knowledge transfer stakeholders.....	28
Figure 10 Cluster 3 - Replication stakeholders	29
Figure 11 Cluster 4 - Replication stakeholders	30
Figure 12 Visits and pageviews over time.....	45
Figure 13 Website visits	46
Figure 14 Websites downloads	46
Figure 15 Social media engagement composition	49
Figure 16 Number of publication by type	51

Executive Summary

The second release of the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication & Progress Report (D7.2) provides an update to the strategies initially outlined in the deliverable D7.1 “Plan for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation”, submitted at M6 of the INHERIT project.

INHERIT is an EU-funded project that aims to develop solutions for the preservation, restoration, and management of cultural heritage (CH) sites. The project promotes the environmental and social sustainability of historic buildings while preserving their cultural value. INHERIT places a particular focus on energy efficiency, resource use and circularity, climate resilience, accessibility, and inclusiveness.

Given the relevance of the project’s objectives and the innovative nature of its solutions, it is essential to implement a coherent strategy for communicating, disseminating, and exploiting project results. To ensure the effectiveness of these activities, an integrated approach has been adopted.

The methodology outlined in this updated plan begins with the identification and assessment of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) based on their current stage of development, along with the definition of preliminary exploitation strategies. This initial phase lays the foundation for understanding the project’s potential impact. As the project advances, more detailed exploitation roadmaps will be developed, including governance models and innovation management practices to support post-project sustainability.

In parallel, a targeted dissemination strategy is being shaped, informed by the ongoing refinement of KERs and stakeholder mapping. This provides a solid basis for the second phase of the project, during which most results will be generated. Communication activities are continuously refined through regular monitoring and reporting to ensure they remain strategic, coherent, and well-aligned with the dissemination and exploitation goals throughout the project’s duration.

The key outcomes of this approach are summarised below, organised by area of interest:

Exploitation strategy

By the end of the project, a total of 11 Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are expected to be reached. They are organised into four thematic clusters based on their nature:

- Cluster 1: Tools and platforms for monitoring and inspection (3 KERs)
- Cluster 2: Modernisation services (4 KERs)
- Cluster 3: Social sciences, humanities outputs, and communication materials (3 KERs)
- Cluster 4: Pilot implementation-related outcomes (1 KER)

All identified KERs are intended for exploitation beyond the project’s duration. Specifically, Cluster 1 outcomes are expected to undergo further development to reach higher Technology Readiness

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Levels (TRLs) and be integrated into service offerings. Similarly, Cluster 2 results are planned for service provision and are also anticipated to contribute to academic research. Cluster 3 outcomes will primarily support knowledge transfer and academic use, while the result in Cluster 4 is foreseen to enable replication efforts in new contexts.

Dissemination strategy

The dissemination strategy is built on the prioritisation of the stakeholders previously identified. The prioritisation used to plan the dissemination activities was informed by regrouping the key stakeholders identified for each exploitation strategy described in the first phase. As a result, three prioritised stakeholder groups were identified for each cluster of results.

The following table summarises the prioritised stakeholders linked to each group of results:

Table 1 Overview of prioritised stakeholders per cluster

Cluster no.	Prioritised stakeholders
Cluster 1	Private and public building owners
	Public authorities and policymakers
	Cultural heritage organisation and association
Cluster 2	Energy efficiency solution providers
	ICT solution providers
	Construction and building industry
Cluster 3	Private and public building owners
	Public authorities and policymakers
	EU initiatives
Cluster 4	Private and public building owners
	Cultural heritage organisation and association
	EU initiatives

These stakeholder groups were selected based on their high level of interest and potential impact across the exploitation strategies. The dissemination strategy is tailored to each result cluster, considering the specific roles of each stakeholder group and identifying the most appropriate dissemination formats to engage them effectively. Additionally, the strategy includes an overview of the most relevant channels and initiatives to maximise outreach and visibility.

Communication strategy

Communication activities complement the exploitation and dissemination strategies by supporting effective outreach to a wider audience and raising awareness of the project's objectives, outcomes,

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

and achievements. The strategy outlined in the first Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) plan has been reviewed and refined based on the results and impact of activities carried out to date. An analysis of data from the main communication channels—including the project website, social media platforms, and editorial publications—indicates overall strong performance and engagement. Based on that, this document identifies the areas of improvement and the activities that must be carried out to reach the corresponding KPIs.

Given that the core strength of the INHERIT project lies in testing its solutions across eight pilot sites, it is essential that communication and dissemination activities, while guided by a central strategy, are adapted to reflect the unique characteristics of each local context. To ensure this, Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Local Desks have been established for each pilot site. These Local Desks serve as a bridge between the overarching strategy and local-level implementation, ensuring coherence, relevance, and effectiveness. The local communication strategies developed by the Desks are compiled in the Annex of this document.

1. Introduction

This document represents the Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report – Deliverable D7.2 – and serves as an update to the initial version submitted at M6. It outlines the progress made in the implementation of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy for the INHERIT project results. The deliverable provides an overview of the activities carried out to date and sets out the updated strategic direction for the upcoming phases of implementation.

A final update will be provided at the end of the project, through the D7.4 Final exploitation plan, which will detail how project results will be used beyond the project's lifetime, and the Final Report on Communication, which will summarise the communication activities and achievements. All information contained in this document is non-sensitive.

The deliverable is structured into five chapters:

1. **Introduction** – Outlines the purpose of the document and presents the integrated methodological approach.
2. **KERs, exploitation strategy, and stakeholders** – Presents the updated results, the strategic exploitation pathways, and the stakeholders analysis per each group of results.
3. **Dissemination strategy** – Summarises the dissemination formats and channels associated with prioritised stakeholders, based on their role.
4. **Communication activities: progress and impact** – Provides an overview of the communication strategies implemented to date and details the monitoring activities to evaluate their effectiveness.
5. **C&D local desks** – Defines the Local Desks, their roles and the approach used to develop local communication and dissemination strategies.

1.1. Update on Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) activities

CDE activities during the first 21 months progressed smoothly and successfully, with no deviations from the original plan. All tasks are ongoing, all deadlines have been met, and several KPIs have already been achieved.

In line with the first dissemination, exploitation & communication plan (D7.1), certain actions and communication and dissemination materials were adapted or expanded to accommodate partners' specific needs, requests, and unforeseen circumstances.

The table below provides an overview of progress for each area.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Table 2 Update of the project's CDE activities

	Description	Status	Result	Deliverables
COMMUNICATION	Design of INHERIT visual identity		Definition of logo, visual elements and brand book	M6 – D7.1 Plan for dissemination, exploitation & communication M21 – D7.2 Second release of the DEC plan and progress report M42 – D7.3 INHERIT report on dissemination & communication activities, & results achieved
	Development of communication kit		A Flyer, a roll-up and a project video were delivered in M6. In addition, an info-sheet with the key expected results per pilot was created.	
	Running project website and social media		Social media channels and the project website have been launched respectively at M2 and M5). The X/Twitter account has been replaced by Facebook at M12. Continuous management and posts are carried out to share the main project news and achievements.	
	Pilot presentation videos		Two pilot presentation videos (Poland and Greece) have been released in English and translated in the local language.	
	C&D Local Desks		C&D Local Desks have been established for each pilot to create and implement a local communication and dissemination strategy. The Local Desks will be maintained until the end of the project.	
DISSEMINATION	Scientific publications		Research articles published on peer-reviewed scientific journals. (1/15 as of the date of this deliverable)	M6 – D7.1 Plan for dissemination, exploitation & communication M21 – D7.2 Second release of the DEC plan and progress report
	Factsheets/Info packs		Concise, accessible documents that summarise key technical information about INHERIT	
	Policy briefs		Short, targeted documents that present research findings and recommendations to policymakers	
	Best practises book		A compiled collection of successful methods and,	

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

			approaches adopted in the pilot areas and that can be replicated or adapted by others.	M42 – D7.3 INHERIT report on dissemination & communication activities, & results achieved
	Clustering activities		Synergies with the three sister projects and other EU projects (e.g. Re-Value, RENOVERTY) have been initiated. Involvement in the Smart Energy Cluster, participation to external events (e.g. Sustainable Places) with the Built4people partnership, BuildingLife Implementation Task Force, and NEB Initiative.	
EXPLOITATION	Preliminary identification of KERs		Identification of 9 KERs	M6 – D7.1 Plan for dissemination, exploitation & communication
	Identification of main stakeholders		Identification and characterisation of 11 groups and 27 subgroups of stakeholders	
	Identification of exploitation pillars		Identification of 6 exploitation pillars for the valorisation of project's results	
	Stakeholder mapping and prioritisation		Correct prioritisation of the stakeholders based on impact-interest	
	Update of KERs according to project implementation		Identification of 11 KERs, development of exploitation roadmaps, and replication roadmaps, identification of business models for the pilots, and identification of exploitation risks.	M21 – D7.2 Second release of the DEC plan and progress report
	Creation of specific exploitation strategies for each KERs		Tailoring of the preliminary strategies on the KERs	M42 – D7.4 Final exploitation plan

1.2. Methodology

The INHERIT project is designed to develop innovative tools and services for the monitoring and maintenance of cultural heritage (CH) sites. These solutions will be validated across 8 pilot sites.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Given the complexity of the project's implementation, a coordinated and integrated strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation is fundamental to the project's success. This strategy not only supports effective outreach throughout the project duration but also ensures that results achieve lasting impact and are effectively applied beyond the project's lifecycle. By clearly communicating objectives and outcomes, widely disseminating key findings, and strategically planning the exploitation of results, INHERIT aims to foster sustainable advancements in CH maintenance that extend well beyond the project's scope and timeline.

Within INHERIT, the integration of CDE activities is pivotal for maximising the uptake and visibility of research outcomes. This chapter outlines the methodological framework that underpins this integrated approach, highlighting the interconnections and synergies across the five methodological steps. Figure 1 provides a visual overview of these steps, which are further detailed in the subsequent sections.

Figure 1 Integrated approach structure

1.2.1. Identification of KERs and IPR management

The starting point of the integrated approach is the identification of the KERs — the primary project outputs with potential for continuous use and impact beyond the project's conclusion. This process began at the project's inception with the definition of an initial set of KERs. The list has since been revised to align with the project's progress and will continue to evolve as implementation advances.

In parallel with the KERs identification, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) aspects — including ownership and anticipated protection measures (e.g. patents, soft IP) — have been assessed and mapped. Due to their confidential nature, these details are not included in this deliverable.

The table below summarises the key activities undertaken as part of this initial step.

Table 3 Process of KER and IPR mapping overview

Timing	Action	Description
M1-M6	Preliminary assessment of KERs and exploitation pillars	Through desk research an initial analysis of the main project's KERs and exploitation pillars has been carried out.
M6	First release of the CDE D7.1	Consolidation of the gathered information and consolidation in the first plan for dissemination, dissemination, and exploitation of project result D7.1
M14	First introductory exploitation workshop during the 2 nd Plenary Meeting in Valladolid.	The first introductory exploitation workshop aimed to familiarise the entire consortium with key exploitation concepts. It covered topics such as: KER, IPR management, TRLs, exploitation strategies, and the overall process.
M18	Second Exploitation Workshop (online)	The second workshop focused on introducing the Library of KERs and SH, namely the tool used to collect information on the results, stakeholders, and IPR issues.
M18	Sharing the first Library of KERs	The first Library of KERs, a tool used for the monitoring of the project results, was shared among all partners to gather information on results and partners' intentions to exploit such results.
M18-19	Gathering and Analysis	The information was collected and analysed to have a mapping and overview of all the project's results.
M20-M21	Analysis and drafting of D7.2	The analysis involved a comprehensive mapping of project results, and laying the groundwork for exploitation strategies. Results of this steps are reported in the current deliverable (D7.2)

1.2.2. Stakeholder mapping

To support the definition of the exploitation strategies and to guide the dissemination activities a comprehensive mapping of the main stakeholders of the project has been conducted. The process started with the identification of the main groups of project stakeholders. Then the stakeholders were prioritised considering their potential interest and impact in the exploitation of the project results.

1.2.3. Dissemination strategies

A coherent dissemination strategy is essential for effectively communicating the project's results to the identified stakeholders. The strategy presented in this document builds on the stakeholder mapping described above, which has been adapted specifically for dissemination purposes.

While the stakeholder mapping for exploitation activities focuses on identifying the most relevant groups based on their impact and interest in specific exploitation strategies, the mapping for

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

dissemination combines all exploitation strategies across each cluster of KERs. This approach enabled us to identify three key stakeholders for each KERs cluster. Based on this, the dissemination strategy outlines the primary formats and channels that will be used to reach these stakeholders, tailored to their roles within the INHERIT project.

Content for each dissemination product will be developed to reflect the needs and interests of the target audience. This content will be created in collaboration with INHERIT partners, leveraging their specific areas of expertise.

1.2.4. Exploitation strategies

After the identification of the results, the assessment of ownership and the identification of stakeholders, exploitation strategies adapted to the types of results and the intentions of the partners were developed. these strategies were developed to ensure and facilitate the maximum impact of the project results after the project.

The process of defining the exploitation strategies is linked to the process described in Table 3.

2. KERs, exploitation strategies and stakeholder mapping

2.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the main KERs developed in INHERIT. The information reported in this chapter represents an update of the information presented in the first release of this deliverable. The results mapped have been divided into four main clusters, reflecting the areas of impact of the project:

1. Cluster 1: monitoring and inspection tools and platforms (3 results).
2. Cluster 2: modernisation services (4 results).
3. Cluster 3: SSH and communication materials (3 results).
4. Cluster 4: Pilot implementation (1 result).

Figure 2 INHERIT results clusters

For each cluster, the results are presented, describing how they will be exploited after the end of the project and which stakeholders are more relevant in terms of impact and interest for the exploitation of project results. The stakeholder analysis also informs and supports the dissemination activities that are presented in the following chapter.

This report presents a total of eleven KERs. Updating the nine KERs that were presented in the first plan (D7.1). The results encompass tools and methodologies for the assessment of the current state of the CH site, as well as services for the modernisation of those CH sites, Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and communication materials for a widespread and social acceptance of the renovation, and pilot implementation.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Given the public character of this deliverable, all results are reported at an aggregate level without disclosing any confidential information. The results will be updated following the project implementation. The updated version of the KERs, IPR strategy, and exploitation strategy will be presented in the D7.4 “Final exploitation plan”.

2.2. Cluster 1: monitoring and inspection tools and platform

2.2.1. KERs and exploitation strategies

The monitoring and inspection tools in INHERIT are developed by Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs), research centres, a university, and a non-profit foundation. Those results encompass tools and platforms that monitor and assess different parameters of CH sites. These results are protocols for technical inspection of heritage buildings, a framework and a dashboard for monitoring and assessing the CH site, and a platform compliant with data from space.

The three results will be used to assess other CH sites. The exploitation pathways will focus, therefore, on expanding the services of the KERs owners, as well as being leveraged for dissemination purposes and replication in other contexts. The following table summarises the preliminary exploitation strategies planned for the results in this cluster.

Table 4 Exploitation strategies for KER2

KER2- Technical inspection protocols for heritage buildings’ more efficient and sustainable (re)use	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRL Upscale • Provision of services • Knowledge transfer
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The owners plan to apply for other Horizon Europe, national, and private-sector funding to further upscale and validate the protocols. In particular, the protocols will be further upscaled and replicated in other European cities. • Once validated, the protocols will be used for commercial and non-commercial purposes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ For commercial purposes, the protocols will be leveraged by the owners to provide or improve existing services. ○ For non-commercial purposes, the protocols will be used for publications on the topic of sustainable maintenance and management of buildings.

Table 4 Exploitation strategy KER2

KER3- INHERIT Monitoring & Assessment Framework and dashboard, aligned with 4 key dimensions

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRL Upscale and Replication • Provision of services
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The framework will be leveraged for commercial and non-commercial purposes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ For non-commercial purposes, the owners plan to further develop and adapt the framework in other CH sites. To sustain these activities, external funding such as other EU initiatives will be evaluated. ○ For commercial purposes, the framework and dashboard will be offered as a service. Collaborations with third parties, ICT service providers and CH entities will be explored to facilitate broader adoption.

Table 5 Exploitation strategy KER5

KER5- Data Space compliant platform for heritage buildings smartification & data exchange	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRL Upscale
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The owner plans to further test and refine the platform. Other European initiatives under the CH context will be considered to refine the result.

2.2.2. Stakeholder mapping

Based on the exploitation strategies, different stakeholders have been mapped and prioritised according to their level of interest and impact on the exploitation of the identified KERs. The following chapter presents the results of the stakeholder analysis for the three exploitation routes envisaged for INHERIT's monitoring and inspection tools and platform.

2.2.2.1. Provision of service

Figure 3 Cluster 1 – Provision of service stakeholders

Key stakeholders include private and public building managers and owners, public authorities, and policymakers—groups that demonstrate both strong interest and high potential impact. As enablers, they possess the authority to drive adoption by mandating or facilitating the use of the project’s outcomes. For instance, public authorities can support the renovation services through legislative measures or dedicated funding, while building managers and owners can directly integrate these solutions into their asset management strategies. Their active engagement is critical to ensuring rapid uptake, regulatory alignment, and broad market diffusion.

Stakeholders from the construction and building industry have a substantial interest in the practical application of the results. These actors are expected to play a dual role: as direct users of the monitoring and inspection services—integrating them into construction or renovation processes—and as promoters of their adoption, by recommending their use to clients or partners. Their involvement is therefore key both as potential customers and as multipliers supporting the operational uptake of the results across the sector.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Solution Providers also represent an important segment, particularly due to their technical expertise and essential role in implementing technological solutions. While their interest and impact are moderate, targeted engagement is vital, as their cooperation supports seamless integration and scalability. Furthermore, specialised stakeholders like energy efficiency solution providers and EU initiatives demonstrate lower direct interest but maintain considerable impact.

Figure 4 Cluster 1 – TRL upscaling stakeholders

For upscaling activities, priority remains with **public authorities and policymakers**, who can enable further development by funding new research initiatives, and with **building managers and owners**, whose engagement is essential for providing additional testing sites. The construction and building industry also shows high levels of interest and impact. These stakeholders can act as key partners in upscaling efforts thanks to their technical expertise and on-the-ground knowledge, which are crucial for adapting and tailoring the services to different building typologies and operational contexts, thus supporting the transition from validated tools to fully integrated market-ready solutions.

Supportive stakeholders such as ICT solution providers and EU initiatives play a key role in enhancing, standardising, and amplifying the technical advancements generated by the project. For example, ICT providers can support the integration of monitoring tools into existing digital platforms or management systems, facilitating interoperability and broader scalability. Similarly, EU initiatives can help amplify visibility and alignment with broader policy goals, creating synergies with ongoing programmes and funding opportunities.

Supportive stakeholders like **ICT Solution Providers** and **EU Initiatives** hold key positions in improving, standardising, and amplifying technical advancements. Conversely, the interest and impact of stakeholders such as **energy efficiency solution providers**, **energy players**, and **academia** tend to be more specific and context-dependent. For instance, an energy efficiency company may be particularly interested in the results when they align with retrofitting interventions targeting building performance upgrades. Likewise, academic stakeholders may engage more deeply when the outcomes contribute directly to ongoing research themes or offer new collaboration

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

opportunities. Their involvement, while potentially valuable, is therefore more selective and often linked to particular use cases or project phases.

2.2.2.3. Knowledge transfer

Figure 5 Cluster 1 – Knowledge transfer stakeholder

For knowledge and dissemination activities, **academia and research centres** are highlighted as crucial stakeholders, emphasising their role in spreading awareness through conferences, scientific events, publications, and academic courses. Additionally, the continued engagement of **private and public building managers and owners** is necessary to embed practical knowledge into daily management practices.

Public authorities and policymakers remain central, given their capability to institutionalise new knowledge through policy, funding, and incentives. Technical intermediaries, including **ICT solution providers, energy efficiency solution providers, and industry representatives**, serve as essential channels for disseminating practical knowledge and facilitating its adoption across various sectors.

2.3. Cluster 2: modernisation services

2.3.1. KERs and exploitation strategies

Within INHERIT, new services for the modernisation of the CH sites are being developed. Universities, research centres, and SMEs are collaborating to achieve the results in this cluster. Three main groups of services, plus a hub of measurement, are being developed. In turn, each service is divided into subservices:

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

- KER 6 “INHERIT design and renovation services” includes services related to the use of AR and VR for the design of CH renovation (sub-6.1); to the simulation and modelling of the environment (sub-6.2), to the renovation planning (sub-6.3), and the comfort optimisation (sub-6.4).
- KER7 “INHERIT monitoring, operation, and management services” encompasses services related to the management of the CH, including energy management services (sub-7.1), the monitoring of CH through digital twin solutions (sub-7.2), and the mobility monitoring (sub-7.3).
- KER8 “INHERIT preservation and maintenance services” encompasses services related to the maintenance of the CH site, including services for the preventive maintenance through H-BIM (sub-8.1), maintenance through GIS-based solution (sub-8.2), and climate scenario (sub-8.3).

Most of these results need further validation through other European projects and in-site testing. Once validated, these results can expand and improve the partner's service portfolio. The following table presents the exploitation strategies for the macro group of services. The singular exploitation strategies for each sub-service will be presented in the final exploitation plan.

Table 6 Exploitation strategy KER4

KER4- INHERIT Hub of measures inventory for cost-effective and less disruptive modernisation of CH sites	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further research • Academic exploitation and knowledge transfer • Service provision
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The owners will utilise the results for other European-founded research projects in the CH buildings topic. Furthermore, being one of the owners a university, the results will be used for academic activities and knowledge transfer with students. Commercial partners will instead use the result for optimising their services in heritage building renovation.

Table 7 Exploitation strategy KER5

KER7- INHERIT monitoring, operation, and management services	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRL upscale • Academic exploitation and knowledge transfer • Replication
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The owners will upscale the readiness of this group of services through alignment and integration with other tools to further expand applicability. Also, the result will be leveraged for academic publications and knowledge transfer with students.

Table 8 Exploitation strategy KER5

KER5- Data Space compliant platform for heritage buildings smartification & data exchange	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic exploitation and knowledge transfer • Service provision • Replication
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The owners of these services will focus on exploiting them through knowledge transfer activities to relevant stakeholders, use them for academic purposes, and expand the portfolio of services, sustainability and heritage building renovation offered by the owners.

Table 9 Exploitation strategy KER8

KER8- INHERIT preservation and maintenance services	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRL upscaling • Service provision • Replication
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The services will be further validated in other European-funded projects. During this phase, owners will integrate these services with other tools and services on CH building monitoring to support climate adaptation and risk-informed heritage management. Once validated, these services will be leveraged by KER owners to develop new commercial services and expand their service portfolio. Potential collaborations with third parties to integrate the tool into existing planning and management platforms will be explored.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

2.3.2. Stakeholder mapping

2.3.2.1. Provision of service

Cluster 2 - Provision of service

Figure 6 Cluster 2 - Provision of service stakeholders

Private and public building managers and owners have the highest impact and a strong interest. As direct beneficiaries, they are central to the adoption of services, particularly those focused on monitoring, renovation, and ongoing building management. Their involvement is fundamental for a successful exploitation of the results. Informing them of the project results is a key aspect to ensure that there is an actual demand for the services.

ICT solution providers and energy efficiency solution providers are critical technical actors for implementation and scaling. Their high interest reflects business alignment, while their impact lies in enabling digital integration, data processing, and efficient energy-related functionalities. Collaboration with these stakeholders is essential for service deployment, interoperability, and performance optimisation.

Construction and building industry actors also show very strong interest and significant impact. As service implementers, their focus on renovation and modernisation services positions them as key players in realising the value of the proposed solutions. Public authorities and policymakers play an enabling role, supporting deployment through funding, policy incentives, and regulatory alignment. Their interest in service provision stems from its potential to support policy objectives in heritage preservation and energy transition.

Cluster 2 - Replication

Figure 7 Cluster 2 - Replication stakeholders

Private and public building managers and owners show the highest interest and impact. Their cross-portfolio responsibilities and practical knowledge make them ideal actors for transferring solutions from pilot sites to broader building stock. Their commitment is essential for scaling the solutions in other contexts. **CH organisations and associations** also show strong interest and impact. Their wide networks, thematic authority, and advisory functions make them multipliers and advocates for wider uptake. **Public authorities and policymakers** are key enablers of replication. Their support through public procurement, funding programmes, or planning regulations can institutionalise the transfer of solutions to new areas. Other stakeholders, such as the **construction and building industry** and **energy efficiency providers**, are crucial for ensuring that solutions are applicable and replicable across diverse technical and environmental contexts. Their involvement supports the adaptation of methods and tools to local conditions and building typologies.

EU initiatives show high interest, particularly where replication aligns with European missions or clusters. While their direct operational impact may be limited, they are important for cross-project integration and high-level dissemination.

Cluster 2 - TRL upscaling

Figure 8 Cluster 2 - TRL upscaling stakeholders

Energy efficiency solution providers show both high interest and the highest impact. Their involvement is essential for validating the services under real operational conditions and ensuring that the solutions align with market and performance requirements. These stakeholders are well-positioned to test, adapt, and potentially integrate the results into their existing commercial offerings.

ICT solution providers and **construction and building industry** actors are also central to the upscaling process. ICT providers ensure that digital components can be integrated, scaled, and maintained within existing platforms. **Construction stakeholders** contribute through prototyping, material testing, and operational feedback. **Energy players** bring infrastructural and systems-level expertise that can support the scalability and resilience of the services.

Public authorities and policymakers can support the upscaling process by facilitating access to pilot sites, enabling public procurement for demonstration, and ensuring that the solutions align with existing policy and regulatory frameworks. Their role is more supportive than operational, but early involvement helps anticipate barriers and foster institutional backing. Academia and research centres and private, and public building managers and owners are not primary drivers of technology development. However, their support sustains further research and early deployment. Their involvement can help assess operational feasibility and user experience.

2.4. Cluster 3: SSH and communication materials

2.4.1. KERs and exploitation strategies

The third cluster of results developed within the project pertains to social science and humanities topics, as well as communication materials. All the results within this area are expected to contribute to increasing awareness of the renovation services through a capacity building program and the creation of a network of contacts. In addition to increasing awareness, these results are related to the development of a framework for a multi-stakeholder knowledge exchange, aimed at improving the inclusiveness of CH.

These results will be exploited beyond the project's conclusion primarily through knowledge-sharing activities and applications in different contexts. Replicating and applying these results in other scenarios will raise awareness of the project's solutions and, more broadly, promote the renovation of CH sites. Additionally, the universities involved in the project will include these outcomes in their academic curricula and educational offerings.

Table 10 Exploitation strategy KER1

KER1- Social Science Framework and multi-stakeholder knowledge exchange for sustainable and inclusive CH	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic exploitation and knowledge transfer • Replication in other contexts
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The result will be used for knowledge transfer activities (publications, articles) and academic exploitation (new courses and PhDs). The results are also expected to be implemented in other contexts, replicating the knowledge exchange in other European regions.

Table 11 Exploitation strategy KER9

KER9- Capacity building programme for durable, yet flexible transformation & energy resilience of communities built around CH assets and policy recommendations towards a sustainable built environment	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic exploitation and knowledge transfer
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The result will be exploited by sharing the capacity building materials to relevant stakeholders (such as the municipality). The capacity building materials will also be used in the academic environment, enriching the academic offer of the university partner.

Table 12 Exploitation strategy KER10

KER10- Network of contacts

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer
Strategy description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The result will be used by the project partners to support the post-project dissemination activities as well as for other communication activities.

2.4.2. Stakeholder mapping

2.4.2.1. Academic exploitation and knowledge transfer

Cluster 3 Academic exploitation and knowledge transfer

Figure 9 Cluster 3 - Knowledge transfer stakeholders

Private and public building managers and owners show the highest levels of both interest and impact. They are a key audience for capacity building initiatives, particularly when these are designed to support the transformation and energy resilience of built heritage environments.

Public authorities and policymakers are equally critical for scaling the effect of knowledge transfer. Their interest is rooted in the need for strategic guidance, policy alignment, and institutional capacity building. They also act as amplifiers, using the materials to inform planning and policy instruments. Collaboration formats such as policy briefs, technical roundtables, and institutional partnerships should be activated early. **CH organisations and associations** also have a very high interest and a strong impact. Their role as mediators between experts, communities, and policymakers allows them to promote the uptake of materials and facilitate knowledge circulation within the heritage sector.

Academia and research centres are both contributors to and users of these materials. They enrich them with research insight and pedagogical methods and ensure long-term transfer through

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

integration into educational programmes and scientific outputs. The **construction and building industry** also show notable engagement. Their high impact score highlights their practical role in applying knowledge to transform built environment. Their involvement helps ensure that transferred knowledge is actionable and technically feasible.

2.4.2.2. Replication

Figure 10 Cluster 3 - Replication stakeholders

Private and public building managers and owners play a key role, thanks to their operational responsibility over building portfolios and their ability to embed participatory processes. Supporting them with adaptable methodologies and tailored replication guidelines will facilitate uptake beyond pilot regions. **Public authorities and policymakers** are also essential to institutionalise and scale the replication process. Their influence on governance frameworks and community planning allows them to promote adoption across different administrative levels and territories.

EU initiatives show very high interest and strong impact. These stakeholders are central for cross-border replication, particularly through alignment with European missions, clusters, and policy agendas. Partnerships with platforms or networks can help amplify reach and contextual adaptability. **Academia** plays a supporting role, offering theoretical foundations and evaluation capacity. Their involvement supports methodological refinement and the creation of context-specific knowledge products. **The construction and building industry**, and **heritage organisations** show moderate engagement. They can act as implementation partners in new territories, especially when replication efforts require adaptation to local materials, cultural values, or operational procedures.

2.5. Cluster 4: Pilot implementation

2.5.1. KERs and exploitation strategies

This cluster of results encompasses all the knowledge related to the pilot implementation and testing of the INHERIT services. During project deployment, the pilot will implement hardware to monitor the state of the CH sites. The installation and the following monitoring procedures allow the pilot owner to gain significant knowledge about their pilot and on the possible activities to improve its efficiency.

Pilot managers can leverage this result to sustain their pilot, as well as for future implementation and replication in other CH sites.

Table 13 Exploitation strategy KER11

KER 11 – Technical implementation in the pilot	
Exploitation strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Replication
Strategy description	The knowledge related to the implementation of the services in the pilot will be leveraged to replicate the project solutions in other CH sites.

2.5.2. Stakeholder mapping

2.5.2.1. Replication

Figure 11 Cluster 4 - Replication stakeholders

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Private and public building managers and owners show the highest levels of both interest and impact. Their practical responsibility over building portfolios and their ability to embed tested solutions into renovation or management workflows make them key drivers of replication. **Public authorities and policymakers** play a strategic enabling role. Their high impact is linked to their authority in approving interventions on built heritage, funding replication, and embedding technical frameworks into policy instruments.

CH organisations and associations are also highly relevant. Their local knowledge, thematic expertise, and community connections make them effective facilitators for contextual adaptation and stakeholder mobilisation. Construction and building industry actors contribute directly to the execution of replication activities. Their interest lies in the opportunity to adopt ready-to-implement solutions and extend their renovation services portfolio. Providing technical specifications, design guidelines, and integration protocols supports their uptake and ensures quality consistency. EU initiatives act as powerful dissemination and coordination platforms. Their interest and impact stem from the potential to embed INHERIT's validated implementation models into other EU projects, policy frameworks, or mission-aligned initiatives.

3. Dissemination strategy

3.1. Prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies

The integrated approach adopted to define the overall CDE) plan requires a tailored dissemination strategy aligned with the key stakeholder groups associated with each cluster of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), as outlined in the previous chapter.

To ensure alignment between stakeholder engagement and dissemination objectives, priority stakeholder groups have been identified for each cluster. These groups result from the combination of the stakeholders with high interest and high impact across the exploitation strategies described above. This chapter details the role played by these stakeholders for each cluster of results and outlines the main dissemination formats and channels best suited to engage them.

The table below summarises the prioritised stakeholders for each group of results.

Table 14 Prioritised stakeholders per cluster

Cluster no.	Prioritised stakeholders
Cluster 1	Private and public building owners
	Public authorities and policymakers
	Cultural heritage organisation and association
Cluster 2	Energy efficiency solution providers
	ICT solution providers
	Construction and building industry
Cluster 3	Private and public building owners
	Public authorities and policymakers
	EU initiatives
Cluster 4	Private and public building owners
	Cultural heritage organisation and association
	EU initiatives

While not listed among the prioritised stakeholders for individual clusters, it is important to emphasise that academia and research centres play a key role across all areas of the project. Their contribution is crucial to the advancement of knowledge, validation of results, and development of innovative methodologies in the field of CH preservation. For these reasons, they will be consistently engaged and actively involved throughout the dissemination process.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

3.1.1. Cluster 1: dissemination strategies

Cluster 1 includes tools and platforms designed to monitor and assess various parameters of CH sites. These results encompass protocols for the technical inspection of heritage buildings (KER2), a framework and dashboard for ongoing monitoring and assessment (KER3), and a platform compliant with data from space (KER5).

The table below outlines the most relevant stakeholder groups for this cluster, along with their roles according to the specific set of results, and the dissemination formats and channels best suited to engage them.

Table 15 Cluster 1: prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies

CLUSTER 1: DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES		
Prioritised stakeholders	Key role for INHERIT	Dissemination formats, channels and networks
Private and public building owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Act as early adopters and facilitators of uptake by integrating the monitoring tools and protocols into heritage building management and renovation practices. Offer new sites for piloting and real-world validation of tools. Recommend the use of such tools in technical and regulatory specifications. 	<p>Formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Factsheets, info-packs to present technical content in a concise, easy-to-read format. Dissemination workshops at the local level to demonstrate practical applications. Training materials and capacity building modules. Final best practices book to showcase tangible impacts and lessons learned. INHERIT final event <p>Channels and networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevant networks and associations: IUT, UIPI, BEUC, COFACE, Euro Coop, Housing Europe, CEPI Relevant events/conferences: European Construction Technology Platform Conference, International Conference on Energy-Saving Building Applications, Energy in Buildings International Conference, International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings.
Public authorities and policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mandate or endorse the adoption of project outcomes in heritage management frameworks. Provide legislative and financial support for the broader uptake of INHERIT-based renovation services. 	<p>Formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy briefs to collect relevant recommendations. Policy roundtables to facilitate dialogue between project partners and national/local policy stakeholders. A white paper outlining the joint recommendations produced with other EU projects.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate upscaling by integrating project results into funding programmes, regional innovation policies, and standardisation efforts. • Institutionalise new knowledge through public policy, procurement rules, and heritage preservation guidelines. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets, info-packs for technical and non-technical decision-makers. • Dissemination workshops with local authorities to demonstrate solutions' application and their benefit. • Final best practices book to showcase the results and encourage policy replication across Europe. <p>Channels and networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and social media accounts • EU Agencies and partnerships: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), Built4People Partnership, New European Bauhaus, Renovation Wave Strategy. • Relevant networks and associations: ICLEI Europe, European Association of Historic Towns and Regions, Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy.
<p>Cultural heritage organisation and association</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the validation and refinement of tools based on heritage management practices. • Facilitate adoption of results by embedding them in conservation protocols and training. • Advocate for uptake across the wider heritage community. • Act as multipliers for dissemination by mobilising their networks and audiences. 	<p>Formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets, info-packs to present technical content in a concise, easy-to-read format. • Dissemination workshops at the local level to present the solutions adopted. • Final best practices book to showcase the results. • Scientific/technical publications (relevant journals: Journal of Cultural Heritage, Journal of cultural Heritage Management; Geo-Information: International Journal of Geo-Information, Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation) <p>Channels and networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and social media accounts • Relevant networks and associations: Europa Nostra, ICOMOS, ICCROM, UNESCO, Architects Council of Europe (ACE), Culture Action Europe • Relevant events/conferences: International Conference on Cultural Heritage Assessment and Art Conservation, International Conference on Heritage Tourism, Cultural Heritage and Preservation, International Conference on Cultural Heritage Assessment and Cultural Conservation.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

3.1.2. Cluster 2: dissemination strategies

Cluster 2 focuses on modernisation services, encompassing tools for design and renovation (KER6), monitoring and management (KER7), and preservation and maintenance (KER8), supported by a measurement hub (KER4).

The table below shows the most relevant stakeholder groups for this cluster, along with their roles according to the specific set of results, and the dissemination formats and channels best suited to engage them.

Table 16 Cluster 2: prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies

CLUSTER 2: DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES		
Prioritised stakeholders	Key role for INHERIT	Dissemination formats, channels and networks
Energy efficiency solution providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable and enhance the energy-related functionalities of INHERIT services. • Provide key insights for tailoring services to technical and environmental contexts. • Validate tools under operational conditions and ensure market alignment. • Contribute to interoperability, system integration, and service optimisation. • Facilitate the replication and scaling of solutions across diverse CH settings. • Support commercial uptake and integration into existing offerings. 	<p>Formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets, info-packs to present technical content in a concise, easy-to-read format. • Dissemination workshops at the local level to demonstrate practical applications. • Final best practices book to showcase tangible impacts and lessons learned. • Scientific/technical publications (relevant journals: Energy and Buildings, Applied Energy, Energy, Energy Policy; IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid, IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery). • INHERIT final event. <p>Channels and networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and social media accounts. • Relevant networks and associations: Big Data Value Association (BDVA), IDSA – International Data Spaces Association, Heritage Europe . • Relevant events/conferences: European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP) Conference, International Conference on Energy-Saving Building Applications, Energy in Buildings International Conference, International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings, European Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (nZEB) Conference, Digital Built Week Europe, Sustainable Places Conference, Enlit Europe.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

ICT solution providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure interoperability, scalability, and reliability of digital solutions in diverse technical environment. • Process, manage, and visualise data collected from heritage sites for simulation, monitoring, and planning. • Support the customisation and adaptation of tools to different user needs, building types, and local conditions. • Facilitate the uptake and future exploitation of the services. 	Formats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets, info-packs to present technical content in a concise, easy-to-read format. • Dissemination workshops at the local level to demonstrate practical applications. • Final best practices book to showcase tangible impacts and lessons learned. • Scientific/technical publications (relevant journals: Foundations and Trends in Machine Learning, Journal of Machine Learning Research, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research, IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Learning, IEEE Transactions on Neuronal Networks and Learning Systems. • INHERIT final event. Channels and networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and social media accounts. • Relevant networks and associations: Big Data Value Association (BDVA), Big Data Europe, IDSA – International Data Spaces Association • Relevant events/conferences: European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP) Conference, International Conference on Big Data Science and Engineering, International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings, European Nearly Zero Energy Buildings Conference, Sustainable Places, Digital Built Week Europe, European Sustainable Energy Week, Enlit Europe.
Construction and building industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable the execution of renovation and modernisation work, directly applying the developed services. • Ensure solutions are feasible and replicable across diverse technical and environmental contexts. • Contribute to the adaptation of methods and tools to local conditions, building typologies, and cultural contexts. • Contribute to the upscaling process by engaging in prototyping, testing 	Formats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets, info-packs to present technical content in a concise, easy-to-read format. • Dissemination workshops at the local level to demonstrate practical applications. • Final best practices book to showcase tangible impacts and lessons learned. Channels and networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and LinkedIn account • Relevant networks and associations: Big Data Value Association (BDVA), Big Data Europe, IDSA – International Data Spaces Association • Relevant events/conferences: European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP)

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

	materials, and providing feedback on operational performance.	Conference, International Conference on Big Data Science and Engineering, International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings, European Nearly Zero Energy Buildings Conference, Sustainable Places, International Conference on Energy-Saving Building Applications, European Sustainable Energy Week, Enlit Europe.
--	---	--

3.1.3. Cluster 3: dissemination strategies

Cluster 3 focuses on social sciences, humanities, and communication materials. It includes a capacity building programme (KER9), a framework for multi-stakeholder knowledge exchange (KER1) and the creation of a network of contacts (KER10).

The following table presents the most relevant stakeholder groups for this cluster, along with their roles according to the specific set of results, and the dissemination formats and channels best suited to engage them.

Table 17 Cluster 3: prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies

CLUSTER 3: DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES		
Prioritised stakeholders	Key role for INHERIT	Dissemination formats, channels and networks
Private and public building owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Act as a key audience for capacity building initiatives focused on energy efficiency, heritage value, and inclusive renovation. Ensure that the knowledge transferred leads to practical, real-world changes in building management. Leverage their operational responsibility over heritage building portfolios to replicate participatory and inclusive renovation models. Serving as multipliers by embedding learned practices into policy, procurement, and planning processes. 	<p>Formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Factsheets, info-packs to present technical content in a concise, easy-to-read format. Dissemination workshops at the local level to demonstrate participatory processes and showcasing how INHERIT's approaches can be applied on the ground. Training materials and capacity building modules designed to build long-term competence among building owners and their networks Final best practices book to showcase tangible impacts and lessons learned. INHERIT final event <p>Channels and networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevant networks and associations: IUT, UIPI, BEUC, COFACE, Euro Coop, Housing Europe, CEPI Relevant events/conferences: European Construction Technology Platform Conference, International Conference on Energy-Saving Building

		Applications, Energy in Buildings International Conference, International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings.
Public authorities and policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale the effect of knowledge transfer by embedding insights into regulations or funding mechanisms. • Act as amplifiers of project results to shape policy instruments at local, regional, and national levels. • Support the institutionalisation and replication of INHERIT's methods. • Promote adoption across different administrative levels and territories. 	Formats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy briefs summarising evidence-based recommendations. • Policy roundtables to facilitate dialogue between project partners and national/local policy stakeholders. • A white paper outlining the joint recommendations produced with other EU projects. • Factsheets, info-packs for technical and non-technical decision-makers. • Dissemination workshops with local authorities to demonstrate solutions' application and their benefit. • Final best practices book to showcase the results and encourage policy replication across Europe. Channels and networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and social media accounts • EU Agencies and partnerships: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), Built4People Partnership, New European Bauhaus, Renovation Wave Strategy. • Relevant networks and associations: ICLEI Europe, European Association of Historic Towns and Regions, Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy.
EU initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support cross-border replication of results by aligning with European missions, partnerships, and priority areas. • Enable policy mainstreaming and visibility at a higher institutional level. • Facilitate coordination and co-dissemination among sister projects. 	Formats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-organisation of joint events • Co-authored white paper on policy recommendations • Application to the Booster to design a joint dissemination strategy • Presentation of INHERIT results in EU-level forums Channels and networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and LinkedIn account • Relevant networks and associations: Big Data Value Association (BDVA), Big Data Europe, IDSA – International Data Spaces Association • Relevant events/conferences: European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP)

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

		Conference, International Conference on Big Data Science and Engineering, International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings, European Nearly Zero Energy Buildings Conference, Sustainable Places, International Conference on Energy-Saving Building Applications, European Sustainable Energy Week, Enlit Europe.
--	--	--

3.1.4. Cluster 4: dissemination strategies

Cluster 4 covers all the knowledge related to the pilot implementation and testing of the INHERIT services (KER11).

The table below shows the most relevant stakeholder groups for this cluster, along with their roles according to the specific set of results, and the dissemination formats and channels best suited to engage them.

Table 18 Cluster 4: prioritised stakeholders and dissemination strategies

CLUSTER 4: DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES		
Prioritised stakeholders	Key role for INHERIT	Dissemination formats, channels and networks
Private and public building owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hold practical responsibility over building portfolios, making them central to implementing and replicating validated solutions. • Integrate tested services into renovation, maintenance, and management workflows. • Act as key enablers of long-term impact, ensuring innovations' transition into practice. • Use pilot results to make data-driven decisions for future CH upgrades. 	<p>Formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets, info-packs to present technical content in a concise, easy-to-read format. • Dissemination workshops at the local level to demonstrate participatory processes and showcasing how INHERIT's approaches can be applied on the ground. • Training materials and capacity building modules designed to build long-term competence among building owners and their networks • Final best practices book to showcase tangible impacts and lessons learned. • INHERIT final event <p>Channels and networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant networks and associations: IUT, UIPI, BEUC, COFACE, Euro Coop, Housing Europe, CEPI • Relevant events/conferences: European Construction Technology Platform Conference,

		International Conference on Energy-Saving Building Applications, Energy in Buildings International Conference, International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings.
Cultural heritage organisation and association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possess deep thematic expertise and local contextual knowledge. • Maintain strong community networks, enabling effective stakeholder mobilisation. • Support local replication and knowledge transfer across different regions and sectors. 	<p>Formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets, info-packs to present technical content in a concise, easy-to-read format. • Dissemination workshops at the local level to present the solutions adopted. • Final best practices book to showcase the results. • Scientific/technical publications (relevant journals: Journal of Cultural Heritage, Heritage, Journal of cultural Heritage Management; Geo-Information: International Journal of Geo-Information, International, Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation) <p>Channels and networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and social media accounts • Relevant networks and associations: Europa Nostra, European, ICOMOS, ICCROM, UNESCO, Architects Council of Europe (ACE), Culture Action Europe • Relevant events/conferences: International Conference on Cultural Heritage Assessment and Art Conservation, International Conference on Heritage Tourism, Cultural Heritage and Preservation, International Conference on Cultural Heritage Assessment and Cultural Conservation.
EU initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as strategic amplifiers for the dissemination and scaling of pilot results. • Can embed INHERIT's models into broader EU policy frameworks and initiatives. 	<p>Formats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-organisation of joint events • Co-authored white paper on policy recommendations • Application to the Booster to design a joint dissemination strategy • Presentation of INHERIT results in EU-level forums <p>Channels and networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT website and LinkedIn account • Relevant networks and associations: Big Data Value Association (BDVA), Big Data Europe, IDSA – International Data Spaces Association • Relevant events/conferences: European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP)

		Conference, International Conference on Big Data Science and Engineering, International Conference on Sustainability in Energy and Buildings, European Nearly Zero Energy Buildings Conference, Sustainable Places, International Conference on Energy-Saving Building Applications, European Sustainable Energy Week, Enlit Europe.
--	--	--

3.2. Clustering, synergies and events attendance

Given that the INHERIT methodology relies on the active involvement of stakeholders in co-creation processes, engaging with them in person at these events is an effective way to strengthen connections between the consortium and its professional audience. For this reason, INHERIT partners took part in networking and clustering events to increase the project's visibility among key stakeholders.

Under Task 7.4, ICLEI is leading INHERIT's participation in European conferences and events to boost synergies and project visibility. A key highlight is the organisation of an INHERIT webinar within the NEB Festival (April 2024), featuring collaboration with NEBStar, CULTUURCAMPUS, and HeritACT. INHERIT also participated in the Urban Future conference in Rotterdam (June 2024).

In particular, project partners have actively participated in a number of relevant events to disseminate project activities and engage with key stakeholders. In total, partners attended twenty-two (22) external events, including conferences, workshops, and policy dialogues at national and European levels. Notable examples include the 5th International Conference on Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings, Sustainable Places 2024, the European Conference on Sustainable Cities and Towns and Energy Days where project-related insights were shared through presentations, panel discussions, or networking activities. This engagement has contributed to raising awareness about the project's objectives and fostering collaboration with the wider research and policy community.

Contacts with sister projects have been established and participation in joint events is foreseen. INHERIT has become a member of the Smart Energy Cluster and applied to the Booster (formerly Horizon Results Booster) to maximise outreach. INHERIT is also part of a network of projects and initiatives aimed at valorising CH and promoting inclusion and sustainability, in which the New European Bauhaus, the Built4People partnership (participating in the B4P booth during Sustainable Places 2024), and HeriTACE and SCENE projects can be mentioned. Opportunities for pilot participation in external initiatives are monitored and presented, in cooperation with other partners and tasks.

So far, INHERIT has collaborated with different EU projects, participating in a webinar from EU project RENOVERTY, together with ODYSEE-MURE and SEED-MICAT, and has been featured by the Re-Value project. It is worth mentioning the joint event carried out by the UU partner and the CALECHE sister project in Visby (SE), in January 2024.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

3.2.1. Collaboration plan

In line with T7.4, ICLEI has developed a collaboration plan to ensure maximum outreach of INHERIT results. To this end, a mapping exercise of relevant initiatives and potential events has been carried out and INHERIT has already applied and collaborated in different events, creating synergies with other EU projects.

The table below outlines the strategy that will be implemented.

Table 19 Collaboration plan

Initiative/Project	Relevance for INHERIT	Future collaboration/participation plan
Built4People partnership	Supports innovation in sustainable transformation of the built environment, including heritage building, aligning with INHERIT's goals on energy efficiency, cultural value, and inclusive design.	Cooperation with other EU-funded projects related to the Built Environment and the New European Bauhaus (E.g. NEBULA, CLIMRES, AEGIR, and MULTICLIMACT).
Smart Energy Cluster	The Smart Energy Cluster unites EU projects advancing smart energy services, digital tools, and inclusive business models to accelerate the energy transition. Its focus on innovation, stakeholder engagement, and energy equity makes it highly relevant for INHERIT.	Promote INHERIT events and results, and monitor potential synergies in Cluster events and webinars. (Cluster has been invited to INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum #2).
New European Bauhaus	The New European Bauhaus (NEB) is an interdisciplinary initiative launched by the European Commission to connect the European Green Deal to people's daily lives, promoting sustainability, aesthetics and inclusion in the built environment.	Collaboration with NEB Prizes winning projects as guest speakers at the INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum and learning partners for capacity building programme for INHERIT Pilots. Attend NEB Festival 2026. Monitor potential synergies in NEB related events and webinars.
Sister projects (SINCERE, CALECHE, HERIT4AGES)	Sister projects of INHERIT, they showcase how CH can drive sustainable, inclusive development. They offer innovative tools, participatory approaches, and cross-sector collaboration models that align with INHERIT's goals of integrating heritage into future-oriented territorial strategies.	Join SINCERE session " <i>Innovation in Sustainable Restoration of Cultural Heritage Buildings</i> ", at the Cultural Heritage and New Technology conference in Wien, 3-5 November 2025.
INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum	Space for knowledge building, mutual learning, collaborative problem-solving, consultation and networking, exploring innovative	Invited similar projects and initiatives, including sister projects and peer learning partners, to participate in the second edition of

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

	approaches to improving energy efficiency in CH buildings, through the lens of the NEB.	the Forum, that happened on June 3, 2025.
Policy Labs	Provide an opportunity for collective work between pilots, learning partners, partners from the consortium, and further relevant stakeholders.	Sister projects will be involved in the development of the second out of three Policy Labs, planned for Spring 2026, and whose findings will be included in a policy brief, produced at the end of the project.
Booster	Formerly called Horizon Results Booster, it's a platform focused on providing tailored services designed to boost the dissemination and exploitation of project results by converting findings into valuable outcomes, and helping maximise a project's outreach by synergising with similar projects in their dissemination efforts.	In collaboration with ICONS, ICLEI is attending meetings with Booster experts and designing a strategy to make the most of the platform.

4. Communication activities: progress and impact

4.1. Monitoring methodology and Community Engagement Index (CEI)

As presented in the first version of this plan, ICONS has developed a specific methodology to monitor and analyse stakeholders' engagement across various communication channels. This approach allows for the combination of outreach and engagement indicators to form composite engagement indexes to analyse the communication and dissemination impacts for each area of activity separately. These indexes include the Website Engagement Index (WEI), Social Media Engagement Index (SEI), and Publication Engagement Index (PEI).

In addition to these separate indexes, ICONS developed the Community Engagement Index (CEI), which integrates all communication activities into one single metric to evaluate the overall impact of a project.

To facilitate the readability, understanding and comparability of these indexes, ICONS normalised them to a range from 0 to 100. The closer the index is to 100, the better the engagement. The definition of the optimal value used for normalisation is based on over 100 projects managed by ICONS.

Table 20 Community Engagement Index (CEI)

Outreach	Engagement	CEI Norm
101,996	12,750	69

With an outreach of 101,996 and engagement of 12,750, the CEI in the first reporting period shows that the project is successfully reaching a broad audience and prompting a good level of interaction. The normalised score of 69 indicates that the overall community engagement level across INHERIT's communication activities is above average. This reflects positively on the effectiveness of the project's communication strategy so far, especially considering it is still in progress.

The following paragraphs provide a breakdown of the individual indexes that compose the CEI.

4.2. Website

The project website serves as the primary communication and dissemination channel, offering updated information to all stakeholders involved. The website was launched in March 2024 (M6) and can be accessed at <http://www.inheritproject.eu/>.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Since its launch, the website has offered a description of the project’s methodology, goals, and expected outcomes, in addition to a detailed description of the pilots and the solution implemented at the local level. The website collects all project updates and provides direct access to its resources. To promote the Multi-Stakeholder Forum, a dedicated webpage was created in November 2024 (M14). The “Multi-Stakeholder forum” page offers an overview of the initiative, including a detailed Q&A section, and has a dedicated space for the events promoted under the initiative.

4.2.1. Website Engagement Index (WEI) and monitoring

Since its launch, the website has reached a total of 12,310 pageviews and 6,147 visits. The engagement indicator shows that 5,424 of these pageviews lasted more than 60 seconds. With a normalisation rate of 80, the Website Engagement Index (WEI) of the INHERIT project proves to be close to the optimal value.

Table 21 Website Engagement Index (WEI)

Outreach	Engagement	WEI Norm
12,310	5,424	80

The chart represented below shows trends in website traffic from its launch in March 2024 to the end of the first reporting period. The trend shows that pageviews consistently remain higher than visits, suggesting visitors are viewing multiple pages per session.

According to the website data, both visits and pageviews spiked in the week when the website was launched and rose again in October-November 2024 when the first Multistakeholder forum was promoted.

VISITS AND PAGEVIEWS OVER TIME

Figure 12 Visits and pageviews over time

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

The chart below offers an overview of the distribution of visits by traffic source. According to the data, most users access the site directly, showing there is a strong awareness of the project. Nearly a quarter of visits come from search engines, indicating a decent visibility of the project in search results.

Figure 13 Website visits

As the website offers direct access to the project's public documents, another relevant aspect worth considering refers to the downloads. The pie chart illustrates the distribution of document downloads, with flyers leading at 33%, followed closely by press releases announcing the launch of the website at 31%.

Figure 14 Websites downloads

Table 22 Communication strategy - website

COMMUNICATION STRATEGY - WEBSITE	
Relevant aspects	Next steps
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The website has reached a total of 6,147 visits in the first 18 months and is likely to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No major updates to the previous plan are foreseen.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

reach the KPI of 20,000 visits by the end of the project.

- Visitors are viewing multiple pages per session, indicating a good level of engagement.
- With 60% of visits coming from direct entries, the project demonstrates strong brand awareness.

- Pilots' pages will be updated as the project proceeds towards a more mature phase.
- Partners are required to inform ICONS about any updates or relevant achievements that can be promoted on the website.

4.3. Social Media

From the early stages of the project, INHERIT adopted a multi-channel social media strategy to maximise visibility and engagement. Given the project's focus on professional stakeholders – commercial companies, policy actors, and researchers – LinkedIn was selected as the primary social media platform. The account was launched to provide a space for sharing updates, achievements, and event highlights with a specialised target audience.

A Twitter/X account was activated as a secondary channel aimed at reaching broader audiences, including citizens, civil society organisations, media, and EU multipliers. This dual-platform approach allowed INHERIT to tailor its content and outreach to different user groups, ensuring that both expert and non-expert communities were informed and eventually engaged.

In July 2024, the project's Twitter/X account was suspended by the platform's administrators. Despite several formal requests from ICONS to reactivate the account, Twitter/X never provided a valid explanation. Considering this, the recent efforts have been redirected toward strengthening LinkedIn activity. In addition, in October 2024, ICONS launched an INHERIT account on Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61566764861106>

To date, ICONS manages three social media platforms on the account of INHERIT: LinkedIn, YouTube, and Facebook.

In April 2024, INHERIT teamed up with the POCITY projects for a joint social media campaign for World Heritage Day. The campaign aimed to highlight the significance of preserving heritage sites within urban and smart cities to promote a more sustainable and greener future.

4.3.1. Social Engagement Index (SEI) and monitoring

During the first reporting period, INHERIT's social media accounts achieved a total of 51,721 impressions and 6,517 engagement actions, including clicks, likes, comments, and shares.

The overall Social Engagement Index (SEI) stands at 70, indicating that the impact of the communication strategy on social media is above average.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Table 23 Social Engagement Index (SEI)

Outreach	Engagement	SEI Norm
51,721	6,517	70

The table below provides a detailed breakdown of performance by platform. LinkedIn generated the highest reach and engagement, reflecting its relevance for professional and research-focused content. Facebook and YouTube, while smaller in reach, showed good engagement rates, both scoring a SEI of 100.

Table 24 Outreach and engagement by platform

Channel	Outreach	Engagement	SEI Norm
X/Twitter	4.797	850	98
LinkedIn	45,881	5,206	63
Facebook	615	112	100
Youtube	428	349	100
Grand Total	51,721	6,517	70

Considering all platforms, INHERIT's audience on social media totals 738 followers, while the number of posts stands at 147.

Table 25 Posts and followers by platform

Channel	Posts	Followers
X/Twitter	40	166
LinkedIn	82	541
Facebook	22	31
Youtube	3	0
Grand Total	147	738

The chart below represents the engagement composition across all platforms, showing that likes and clicks are the most frequent types of interactions, primarily occurring on LinkedIn.

SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT COMPOSITION

Figure 15 Social media engagement composition

Table 26 Communication strategy – social media

COMMUNICATION STRATEGY – SOCIAL MEDIA	
Relevant aspects	Next steps
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With 738 followers on social media, the project is on track to reach its KPI of 800 total followers. • The X/Twitter account has been replaced with Facebook. • A joint social media campaign was launched in Month 7, helping to achieve one-third of the corresponding KPI (three campaigns are foreseen in total). • LinkedIn is the channel with the highest level of interaction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 2 social media campaigns are already planned • INHERIT’s presence on Facebook will be strengthened. • LinkedIn will remain the key platform for reaching the INHERIT audience.

4.4. Editorial publications

The editorial production covers another pivotal role in communicating INHERIT to its audience, remaining consistently active from the beginning of the project until its conclusion. Each type of publication has been thoroughly described in the initial version of this plan,

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

4.4.1. Publication Engagement Index (PEI) and monitoring

Data from the first reporting period show that the publications reached a total outreach of 53,136. This indicator includes impressions from social media posts linked to publications, website pageviews related to publication content and views on multiplier platforms where the publications were shared.

The total engagement, calculated from interactions on social media posts and the number of downloads from multipliers, stands at 2,307.

The Publications Engagement Index (PEI) stands at 23, indicating that there is room for improvement in generating higher levels of interactions.

Table 27 Publication engagement index (PEI)

Outreach	Engagement	PEI Norm
53,136	2,307	23

The table below provides a detailed breakdown of performance by publication type. Videos stand out as the most engaging format, generating 978 interactions from a more modest outreach of 3,046, highlighting their high effectiveness in capturing audience attention. On the other hand, press releases, despite achieving the highest outreach (39,848), saw comparatively low engagement (267), indicating a lower interaction rate.

Overall, the data indicates that more interactive or visually engaging content tends to produce higher engagement relative to reach.

Table 28 Outreach and engagement by type

Publication type	Outreach	Engagement
Press Release	39,848	267
News Release	5,549	307
Video	3,046	978
Project update	2,614	249
Social media clips	1,189	434
Newsletter	890	72
Grand Total	53,136	2,307

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

The following chart summarises the number of editorial publications by type, based on a total of 22 editorial publications issued in the first reporting period.

NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS BY TYPE

Figure 16 Number of publication by type

A newsletter featuring key updates and relevant achievements is issued every six months and delivered to a list of subscribers. At M18, the INHERIT newsletter has 110 subscribers.

Table 29 Communication strategy – editorial publications

COMMUNICATION STRATEGY – EDITORIAL PUBLICATIONS	
Relevant aspects	Next steps
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Videos stand out as the most engaging format, while press releases - thanks to the role of multipliers - have the highest level of outreach. With 11 news/press releases, the corresponding KPI of 10 has already been reached. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Audio-visual content will remain a priority Partners are required to inform ICONS about any updates or relevant achievements that can be promoted via editorial publications.

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

4.5. Timeline

The table below shows the main communication activities foreseen in the next months. The release of news items and press releases is ongoing.

Table 30 Timeline of communication activities

When	What
M21-23	1 st journalistic article
M22-24	3 rd Pilot video
M24	2 nd social media campaign
M24-26	3 rd newsletter
M24-27	4 th and 5 th Pilot videos
M30-32	4 th newsletter
M31	3 rd social media campaign
M28-38	6 th , 7 th and 8 th Pilot videos
M36-38	5 th newsletter
M38-41	2 nd journalistic article
M42	6 th newsletter

5. C&D Local Desks

5.1. Local C&D strategies and plans

5.1.1. C&D Local Desks: definition and purpose

INHERIT is a complex project, implemented across 8 demo sites, each of which must align with a shared strategy that needs to ensure coherent and coordinated local C&D activities. To bridge the gap between the specific contexts and the project at the general level, a C&D Local Desk was established at each demo site.

As outlined in D7.1, C&D Local Desks serve as the main contact point between the project's C&D Secretariat (ICONS, ICLEI, and EAHTR) and the pilot cities, and vice versa. While the C&D Secretariat was established at the start of the project with the responsibility to design and implement a unified C&D strategy, Local Desks serve as representatives to carry out local C&D activities with the aim to:

- Facilitate the exchange of information and local updates with the C&D Secretariat
- Spread information about the project locally
- Promote and carry out INHERIT-related local activities
- Engage local stakeholders

Given the different socio-economic and geographical contexts of the pilot sites, a tailored approach to C&D was required. This is the reason why Local Desks have been asked to set up their own local C&D strategy.

5.1.2. Roles and responsibilities of the Secretariat

The Local Desks' Secretariat must coordinate, facilitate, encourage, and support local C&D activities, along with tracking their activities. It is the main reference for Local Desks to gather relevant updates at the general project level.

The three partners constituting the Secretariat provide a different type of support:

- **ICONS** provides guidelines and support on C&D content and formats. It's responsible for providing Local Desks with support materials, coordinating joint C&D actions (ex. Campaigns) and monitoring the overall advancement through periodical calls and tracking templates.
- **ICLEI Europe** supports Local Desks by encouraging iterative stakeholder mapping to keep track of key players and their evolving roles. This should involve active engagement to listen to and address stakeholder needs via regular feedback sessions as part of ongoing project-related events and targeted communication campaigns conducted by the local partners (preferably in the local languages). The communication process with timely updates on project developments should be conducted via newsletters, websites, and social media, ensuring transparency and maintaining engagement.
- **EAHRT** encourages and supports Local Desks in participating to external events aimed at promoting the project and creating a network. It helps identify relevant events, conferences

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

and workshops, support local desks with applications, and helps them organise content and communication materials. It is also responsible for tracking all events attended or organised by the local desks.

Since many local activities are connected to WP2, C&D activities are also and will be based on various WP2 activities (ex. Social Labs). To do so, the Secretariat continuously coordinates and collaborates with ZSI (leader of WP2) and directly interacts with local partners already involved in WP2.

5.1.3. Roles and responsibilities of the Local Desks

Overall, the main role of the Local Desk is to oversee communication and dissemination (C&D) activities at the local level. These activities will primarily be conducted in the local language. In particular, each Local Desk should:

- Organise local activities, including events and workshops
- Organise and manage local engagement with citizens and other stakeholders
- Distribute project content to the cities
- Maximise outreach to other cities within their country
- Ensure local coverage of INHERIT news for the target audience
- Collaborate on the dissemination of INHERIT content through local social media
- Provide local content to the C&D Secretariat for EU-level dissemination
- Track and monitor C&D activities (e.g., events, initiatives, press releases, videos, flyers, etc.) at the local level and share the information with ICONS by filling in the dedicated templates
- Implement a local C&D plan
- Guarantee the implementation of the guidelines and actions described in the local C&D plan

5.1.4. Local Desks composition, setup and maintenance

As the first step, Local Desks' contact persons were identified, based on the people already involved in WP2. The table below summarises the persons responsible for C&D activities at the local level.

Table 31 Local Desks composition

Pilot n°	Country	City	Partner	Contact persons	E-mail address
1	Croatia	Jastrebarsko	REGEA	Petra Vučetić Osonjački	pvosonjacki@regea.org
2	France	Noisiel	BYCN	Xavier Gauvin	x.gauvin@bouygues-construction.com
3	Greece	Athens	ELLET	Katerina Stebili	sepi@ellinikietairia.gr

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

				Elias Sakellaris	sak@ellinikietairia.gr
4	Latvia	Riga	RPR	Aija Zucika	aija.zucika@rpr.gov.lv
				Agris Kamenders	Agris.Kamenders@rtu.lv
5	Poland	Gdynia	FASADA	Magdalena-Bogucka Dzik	m.dzik@prefasada.pl
				Agnieszka Łukaszewska	a.lukaszewska@prefasada.pl
6	Spain	Valladolid	CARTIF	María Esteban Ferrer	marest@cartif.es
				Carla Rodriguez Alonso	caraln@cartif.es
7	Sweden	Visby	UU	Gustaf Leijonhufvud	gustaf.leijonhufvud@konstvet.uu.se
				Petra Eriksson	petra.eriksson@konstvet.uu.se
				Andrew Barney	andrew.barney@geo.uu.se
				Heracles Polatidis	heracles.polatidis@geo.uu.se
8	Türkiye	Izmir	IBB	Tutku AYTÜRK	tutkuay@gmail.com
				İpek AKBAYLAR HAYRETER	ipekakbaylar@gmail.com

After identifying contact people, a kick-off call was organised in M6 to clarify roles and responsibilities. Regular meetings (approx. every 2 months) are scheduled to ensure smooth internal communication between partners and ICONS. Meetings can be either dedicated to Local Desks only or integrated with WP7 or WP2 meetings.

The Local Desks will be maintained during the whole project duration.

5.1.5. A tailored C&D strategy for Local Desks

Each Local Desk developed a tailored Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Plan, following a common structure provided by ICONS and aligned with INHERIT's overarching strategy (Deliverable D7.1). While this common framework ensured consistency across all sites, each plan was adapted

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

to reflect the specific needs, contexts, and capacities of the respective countries, demonstrators, and partners.

To support the development of these local plans, the C&D Secretariat organised a collaborative workshop followed by individual consultations with each Local Desk, helping align their strategies with local priorities and opportunities. The local plans identify suitable online and offline channels and formats to ensure effective communication and engagement within each pilot site. Content may be produced in English and/or local languages, depending on the target audience, to maximise reach and accessibility. This section provides an overview of the channels, formats, editorial content, and events selected by the eight demonstrators for their local C&D activities.

5.1.5.1. Channels

Local Desks will use digital channels—including institutional and corporate websites, social media platforms, and media multipliers—to disseminate updates, project milestones, scientific publications, and other relevant content. Social media will primarily be used to share videos, project highlights, and campaign materials.

Each demonstrator will use the existing platforms, such as municipal or institutional websites and corporate or personal social media accounts. Where needed, local-language pages for each pilot site may be added to the INHERIT website. ICONS will coordinate the creation and integration of these pages. Additionally, INHERIT-branded local social media accounts featuring only project-related content may be launched based on the specific needs of each demonstrator.

5.1.5.2. C&D Formats and materials

The formats and materials used by Local Desks will align with those outlined in D7.1, supporting the dissemination of project progress and results to local stakeholders and communities.

Some content has been or will be translated into local languages to improve local engagement. Two formats— roll-ups and pilot videos —have already been adapted. Furthermore, two additional format categories have been introduced to enhance local dissemination efforts:

- Info-sheets: Concise summaries of INHERIT and its services to distribute to stakeholders.
- Additional promotional materials: Items such as gadgets, certificates of attendance, posters, and branded name tags used during workshops and public events to boost visibility and interaction.

The table below summarises the main formats that will be adopted for C&D at the local level.

Table 32 C&D formats for Local Desks

Material/Format	Description	Context of use
Videos	The project presentation video is used by local desks to provide a general overview of the project during events. Each local desk is also involved in the creation of videos, especially video interviews and video-presentation of their demo site (which are included in the general C&D strategy of INHERIT).	Online and offline events and presentations. Social media animation.
Roll-Up	Local desks use the roll-up during physical events organised by the partners and/or by external organisations. Translated roll-up in each local language were made available to the demonstrators.	Offline events
Flyer	Local desks are supposed to distribute printed copies during events and to upload the digital version on websites and spread it through social media.	Offline events. Websites and social media
Project PPT presentation	A project PPT presentation was provided to all INHERIT partners. Local desks can personalise it and use it to present the project during their own or third parties' events (including online and offline workshops, webinars etc.)	Online and offline events and presentations.
Info sheets	Info sheets in English were provided by ICONS as a support communication and dissemination material. Local desks can use both a general and a technical info sheet to spread more detailed information on the project to different types of audiences.	Digital channels. Offline events.
Further INHERIT branded materials (gadgets, participation certificates, name tags etc.)	Further communication materials can be produced by local desks using the INHERIT visual identity, to maximise stakeholders' engagement during workshops and events. Each Local Desk will be responsible for producing and distributing its own gadgets.	Offline events
Factsheets and Info packs	Towards the project's end, all local desks will contribute to the creation of factsheets and info packs, providing relevant content, data, and results. Local desks are also supposed to spread these dissemination materials within their networks and local stakeholders, to foster knowledge transfer and the project's exploitation and replication.	Online and offline
Best practices book	Local desks will contribute to the creation of a best practices book based on the project results, providing evidence of the actions carried out in the demo sites and of their benefits. Local desks are supposed to spread the best practices book within their networks and local stakeholders.	Online and offline

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Material/Format	Description	Context of use
Press and News Release	Local desks' C&D plan implies the production of press and news releases in local languages and their distribution through local digital channels. The content of each depends on the progress of the demo site and might be connected to local events, partnerships or other relevant milestones. The Secretariat also encourages the translation and local distribution of general project updates (i.e. press and news releases regarding the overall project's results)	Online
Newsletters	Local news and events will be spread and promoted not only through website pages and social media but possibly also through newsletters of institutions and organisations involved.	Online

5.1.5.3. Events and Clustering

INHERIT partners will participate in networking and clustering events and activities to raise the project's visibility within the stakeholders' community. Since the inheritance methodology provides for the active involvement of stakeholders in co-creation processes, pilot leaders will meet them in person through events that can effectively raise the engagement between the project consortium and their professional target audience. Three to four Social Labs (i.e. co-creation workshops) will be organised by each pilot, within WP2 and with the support of WP2 leaders and contributors (i.e. ZSI, REGEA).

Aside from scientific conferences, partners, including pilot leaders are encouraged and assisted in the presentation of the project and its results, both during and after the end of the project (including during conferences, workshops, and webinars). In particular, INHERIT C&D local desks are expected to organise communication and dissemination activities, namely:

- 8 dissemination workshops (1 per pilot);
- 8 final dissemination workshops (1 per pilot)

Given the high number of events that the INHERIT partners are expected to attend (50 events by the end of the project), the Local Desks' secretariat, particularly EAHTR, is responsible for supporting local desks in identifying relevant local events to participate in and for providing them with useful communication materials. EAHTR will also be responsible for collecting inputs from local desks, tracking all events organised or attended.

6. Conclusions

The second release of the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication & Progress Report (D7.2) outlines the overarching strategy designed to maximise the impact of INHERIT's results in the coming months.

The document highlights the interconnections between the strategies for each area, built on an integrated approach. The methodology adopted to enhance the project's impact begins with the identification and assessment of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) based on their current stage of development, alongside the definition of preliminary exploitation strategies. The analysis conducted on the INHERIT project highlighted two additional results, for a total of 11 KERs that will be exploited in different ways by the partners. Depending on the type of result and the nature of the partner, the results will be used for providing new commercial services or for academic and knowledge transfer activities. Results related to the pilots will also be used for replication activities. These intermediate results lay the groundwork for more detailed exploitation planning as the project advances, to ensure long-term sustainability beyond the project's lifetime.

Based on this first phase, a focused dissemination strategy is being developed, guided by a prioritisation of stakeholders for each cluster of KERs previously identified. This evolving strategy supports the effective rollout of the project's second phase, when most results are expected. Communication activities are also regularly monitored and adjusted to maintain strategic coherence and alignment with the overarching dissemination and exploitation objectives throughout the project.

The following table summarises the next steps for each area, along with the corresponding deliverables.

Table 33 Overview of INHERIT's CDE next steps

	Next steps	Deliverables
COMMUNICATION	<p>The project website will remain the primary communication channel, providing up-to-date information to a broad audience through news, press releases, and project updates. To ensure a continuous flow of content, partners will be engaged through WP7 meetings and encouraged to share key updates and achievements. INHERIT's presence on social media will be maintained on LinkedIn and Facebook, with a specific objective to grow the fanbase on Facebook. The remaining pilot videos will be produced according to a defined schedule. As audio-visual formats have proven effective for outreach and engagement, these videos will play a key role in promoting local-level activities. Two journalistic articles are planned. At the local level, Local Desks will implement their strategies using both online and offline channels to share content in their local languages.</p>	<p>M42 – D7.3 INHERIT report on dissemination & communication activities, & results achieved</p>

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

DISSEMINATION	<p>Key findings and results will be shared through scientific publications targeting academia, research centres, and technical stakeholders. To facilitate the dissemination of technical results, accessible, easy-to-read formats will be developed, including factsheets and info-packs. To support the integration of these solutions into future policies, key recommendations for policymakers will be compiled in policy briefs, and policy roundtables will be organized to foster dialogue between project partners and national/local policy stakeholders. Training materials and capacity building modules will be developed to build long-term competence among building owners and their networks. Ultimately, a best practice book will collect the pilot achievements to support the replication of INHERIT's solutions in other contexts. ICLEI and EAHTR, among other partners, will help disseminate the final results across their respective networks and within project clusters such as the Smart Energy Cluster and the Build4People partnership. ICLEI and ICONS will make use of the Booster platform to boost the dissemination efforts, transforming project results into concrete valuable outcomes.</p>	M42 – D7.3 INHERIT report on dissemination & communication activities, & results achieved
EXPLOITATION	<p>Based on the results of the conducted analysis, the next steps will involve further refinement and development of the exploitation strategies to ensure optimal alignment with the characteristics of the identified results and the profiles of the respective partners. Special attention will be dedicated to managing joint results and achieving consensus on shared strategies. Additionally, a particular focus will be placed on Intellectual Property management, proactively identifying and addressing any potential IP conflicts.</p>	M42 – D7.4 Final exploitation plan

Annexes

Annex 1 – Local C&D strategies

This annex compiles the strategies developed by the Local Desks. Due to a change in the pilot area in France, the following section does not include a strategy for the French pilot.

6.1.1. Pilot: Jastrebarsko, Croatia

Partners: REGEA

Online strategy

Channel	Target	Specify Channel	Formats
Website	All stakeholders (i.e. ICT solutions providers, Energy players, construction industry, citizen etc.)	REGEAS's website City of Jastrebarsko website	Website news, Press Releases, event promotion
Social Media	All stakeholders	REGEA's LinkedIn and Facebook pages Possible creation of a dedicated page for the INHERIT pilot	Social media campaigns, video posting, events promotion in collaboration with ICONS; newsletter reshare

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Newsletter	All stakeholders	REGEA's newsletter	Entire newsletter; News in existing newsletter
Direct mailings	All stakeholders	Dissemination of relevant content to stakeholders, academia etc.	Info-packs, scientific publications; best practices book; policy briefs, training materials; news

Offline strategy

Action	Specify
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Labs • Participation in national conferences • Policy roundtables • Citizen engagement activities with local schools and universities
Distribution of materials	Distribution of project flyer during events and inside the pilot building Roll-up, info-sheets, branded gadgets, certificates of attendance, info-sheets Pilot specific materials in national language

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Use of digital materials during events	Project PPT presentation, project presentation video and pilot video Results and progress infographics
Other media/activities	Local radio station Mayor's official communications

6.1.2. Pilot: Athens, Greece

Partners: ELLET, ICCS, UPRC, SGL

Online strategy

Channel	Target	Specify Channel	Formats
Website	All stakeholders (i.e. ICT solutions providers, Energy players, construction industry, citizen etc.)	Organizations' websites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ellet.gr • Epu.ntua.gr • Singularlogic.eu • Teeslab.unipi.gr 	Website news, Press Releases, event promotion

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Social Media	All stakeholders	ELLET social media pages (facebook, instagram, X, linkedin, youtube)	Social media posts, video posting, events promotion
Newsletter	All stakeholders	The newsletter of ELLET is abandoned, and the news are directly sent via mail to the members. Regarding INHERIT there was no interest to make one for the programme.	Entire newsletter; News in existing newsletter
Media multipliers	Actors in the building industry, building end-users, citizens, policy enablers	Publication of scientific papers in academic and scientific journals	Dissemination of scientific papers, press releases, journalistic articles
Direct mailings	All stakeholders	Dissemination of relevant content to stakeholders, academia, policymakers, students etc. through ELLET's mailing list	Ex. Info-packs, scientific publications; best practices book; policy briefs, training materials
Other	All stakeholders	Blog news in ELLET's website	

Offline strategy

Action	Specify
--------	---------

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Events	Social Labs (social roundtables) Lab project regarding the creation of a small manual regarding the energy performance and upgrading of cultural heritage buildings (citizen engagement activities) Learning Partner Meeting in Slovenia At the moment, there is no scheduled participation in other external conferences, policy roundtables, citizen engagement activities, booths, roadshows
Distribution of materials	Project flyer, Roll-up, certificates of attendance, info-sheets
Use of digital materials during events	Project PPT presentation, project presentation video and pilot video

6.1.3. Pilot: Riga, Latvia

Partners: RPR

Online strategy

Channel	Target	Specify Channel	Formats
Website	All stakeholders (i.e. ICT solutions providers, Energy players, Riga municipality and its' organizations like Riga energy agency, who are involved in AVE SOL energy management and renovation process, representatives from	Riga planning region website, Riga city website www.rpr.gov.lv ; www.riga.lv	Website news, Press Releases, event promotion, information about public procurements for AVE SOL building

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

	construction sector, AVE SOL visitors and users (choirs) etc.)		
Social Media	All stakeholders	Riga planning region Linked in and Facebook account	Social media campaigns, video posting, events promotion, results publishing about the data gathering or other technical analyse of the building energy management.
Newsletter	All stakeholders	Riga planning region newsletter which is published once per quartal	News in existing Riga planning region newsletter
Media multipliers	Actors in the building industry, building end-users, citizens, policy enablers	www.leta.lv LETA is a Latvian company that provides news agency services. The company delivers news and business information solutions to organisations and businesses.	Dissemination of press releases, articles that are created by Riga planning region.
Direct mailings	All stakeholders	Dissemination of relevant content to stakeholders, academia etc.	Information about project outcomes: scientific publications; best practices book; policy briefs, training materials

Offline strategy

Action	Specify
--------	---------

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Events	Social Labs, participation in external conferences, policy roundtables, citizen engagement activities, booths, seminars and conferences related to energy management and building renovation topics.
Distribution of materials	Project flyer, Roll-up, info-sheets, branded gadgets, certificates of attendance, info-sheets.
Use of digital materials during events	Project PPT presentation, project presentation video and pilot videos (Riga planning region has made professional outdoor and indoor videos of AVE SOL building).
Other media/activities	Individual interviews in thematic radio broadcasts about project results: energy management in CH sites.

6.1.4. Pilot: Gdynia, Poland

Partners: FASADA

Online strategy

Channel	Target	Specify Channel	Formats
Website	All stakeholders (i.e. ICT solutions providers, Energy players, construction industry, citizen etc.)	Fasada website	Website news, Press Releases, event promotion, article/page dedicated to INHERIT and the Polish pilot
Social Media	All stakeholders	FASADA LinkedIn and X posts about social labs and events	Social media posts, video posting, events promotion

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Newsletter	All stakeholders	Not relevant, due to many emails we got information that the newsletter should not be sent	-
Media multipliers	Actors in the building industry, building end-users, citizens, policy enablers	Local website of the Municipality of Gdynia https://www.gdynia.pl/energetyczna/	Article about project and pilot
Direct mailings	All stakeholders	Dissemination of relevant content to stakeholders, academia, local administration (personal contacts)	Info-packs, scientific publications; best practices book; policy briefs, training materials
Other	All stakeholders	Contest for the short video about sustainable, inclusive and resilient Pilot #5 for students and professionals	video

Offline strategy

Action	Specify
Events	Social Labs and local events include citizen engagement activities, lecture about INHERIT for students of the architecture, visiting pilot site
Distribution of materials	Project flyer, Roll-up in polish, info-sheets, INHERIT branded gadgets

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Use of digital materials during events	Project PPT presentation in polish, project presentation video, and pilot video
Other media/activities	Lecture about NEB and INHERIT at the Technical University of Gdansk for students of architecture.

6.1.5. Pilot: Valladolid, Spain

Partners: CARTIF, CEMOSA

Online strategy

Channel	Target	Specify Channel	Formats
Website	All stakeholders (i.e. ICT solutions providers, Energy players, construction industry, citizen etc.)	CARTIF website	Website news, Press Releases, event promotion, blog posts
Social Media	All stakeholders	CARTIF social media pages: LinkedIn, X CEMOSA LinkedIn page	Social media posts, video posting, events promotion, reshare of website and blog content
Newsletter	All stakeholders	Creation of a newsletter in Spanish to be sent to local stakeholders (contacts form CARTIF and CEMOSA), supported by ICONS	Entire newsletter; News in an existing newsletter
Media multipliers	Actors in the building industry, building end-users, citizens, policy enablers	Local newspapers websites: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • El norte de Castilla • Diario de Valladolid 	Dissemination of press releases, journalistic articles about the project's and the pilot's progress

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Direct mailings	All stakeholders	Dissemination of relevant content to stakeholders, academia through the newsletter	Info-packs, scientific publications; best practices book; policy briefs, training materials
Local TV	All stakeholders, mainly citizens	Presentation of the project and pilot in a programme of the local TV to reach all citizens	TV streaming and saved on Youtube
Other	All stakeholders	Blog posts in CARTIF website	

Offline strategy

Action	Specify
Events	Social Labs, participation in external conferences and events (international and local), students' engagement in collaboration with local universities
Distribution of materials	Project flyers, Roll-up, info sheets, branded gadgets, certificates of attendance
Use of digital materials during events	Project PPT presentation, project presentation video and pilot video
Other media/activities	Local newspapers websites: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • El norte de Castilla • Diario de Valladolid

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

6.1.6. Pilot: Visby, Sweden

Partners: UU

Online strategy

Channel	Target	Specify Channel	Formats
Website	All stakeholders (i.e. ICT solutions providers, Energy players, construction industry, citizen etc.)	UU website	Project description and information.
Social Media	All stakeholders	Linkedin, Facebook and Instagram via Building Conservation Department	Social media campaigns, video posting, events promotion. Website news, Press Releases, event promotion, photos and contact persons
Media multipliers	Actors in the building industry, building end-users, citizens, policy enablers	World Heritage group. Swedish Energy Agency.	Journal articles
Direct mailings	All stakeholders	Dissemination of relevant content to personal contacts	Info-packs, scientific publications; best practices; policy briefs, training materials

Offline strategy

Action	Specify
--------	---------

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Events	Social Labs Joint events with other projects (i.e. Caleche) Participation in external conferences Policy roundtables at the “political week” in Visby, Joint exhibition with sister projects during the political week in Visby summer 2026
Distribution of materials	Project flyer, Roll-up, posters, info-sheets presented and distributed during social labs and in the university
Use of digital materials during events	Project PPT presentation, project presentation video and pilot video
Other media/activities	Participation to local radio programmes Publication of journalistic articles on the “Gotland Tidning” local newspaper University lectures for undergraduates and postgraduates BSc and MSc thesis topics related to INHERIT and the Swedish pilot BSc distance education assignments related to INHERIT

6.1.7. Pilot: Izmir, Turkey

Partners: IBB

Online strategy

Channel	Target	Specify Channel	Formats
Website	All stakeholders (i.e. ICT solutions providers, Energy players, construction industry, citizen etc.)	Organization/Municipality website www.izmir.bel.tr	Website news, Press Releases, event promotion

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Social Media	All stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instagram: izmirbuyuksehirbelediyesi, izmirtubetv • Instagram: apikam.izmir (account on the events taken place in the pilot building) • LinkedIn: Izmir Buyuksehir Belediyesi • Twitter: izmirbld • YouTube: IzmirTube • Facebook: İzmir Büyükşehir Belediyesi 	Social media campaigns, video posting, events promotion We share the Social Lab events' outcomes in our personal LinkedIn accounts
Newsletter	All stakeholders	Local newsletter of IBB (Bizizmir.com)	Entire newsletter; News in existing newsletter
Media multipliers and e-magazines	Actors in the building industry, building end-users, citizens, policy enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yesilgazete.org (e-newspaper) • Yeniasir.com.tr (both printed and e-newspaper) • Egedesonsoz.com (e-newspaper) • Egeninsesi.com (e-newspaper) • Egemimarlik.org (both printed and e-journal) • Yapidergisi.com (both printed and e-journal) • Yuvamdunya.org (website) • Megaronjournal.com (e-journal) 	Dissemination of press releases, and journalistic articles; news reshare
Direct mailings	All stakeholders	Ex. Dissemination of relevant content to stakeholders, personal contacts: Academic stakeholders from almost all the universities of İzmir, who can support in sharing content with the relevant academics & students	Ex. Info-packs, scientific publications; best practices book; policy briefs, training materials
Other	All stakeholders	Ex. Podcast, blogs etc.	

Second release of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication & progress report / D7.2

Offline strategy

Action	Specify
Events	<p>Social Labs, participation in external conferences, policy roundtables, and citizen engagement activities such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inclusion of students in a Lab Project about the CH of Izmir and energy-efficient solutions in historical buildings - Collaboration with academic consultants and their PhD students as contributors to the project - Study Visit host in Slovenia - Combination of the Study visit with the 17th International “ERBE” Symposium on Cultural Heritage in Geosciences, Mining and Metallurgy – Libraries – Archives – Museums (22-27 Sept 2025)
Distribution of materials	<p>Project flyer, Roll-up, info-sheets, event posters</p> <p>We use roll-up and event posters in the conference hall where the Social Labs take place. We email our stakeholders info-sheets about the events.</p>
Use of digital materials during events	<p>Project PPT presentation, professional video presentation about Izmir city in general and the pilot building in detail, social media infographics (not produced yet).</p> <p>Results of the surveys for stakeholders and Mentimeter sessions during events.</p>
Other media/activities	<p>Possible collaboration with academic stakeholders and PhD students in developing Inherit project outputs.</p>